

H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program 2024 Annual Report

Executive Summary

The Maumee River, adjacent to the H2Ohio Forder Bridge Floodplain Reconnection Project.
Photo credit: Genna Hunt

Please cite this document as: Lake Erie and Aquatic Research Network, Wetlands and Water Quality Group. 2025. H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program: 2024 Annual Progress Report, Executive Summary. Ohio Department of Natural Resources, Office of Coastal Management

The present volume (Executive Summary, Volume 1) of the 2024 Annual Report describes the key H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program results from the Water Year 2024 (October 1, 2023–September 30, 2024).

Note: The data and management summaries contained in this report are provisional. Every effort has been made to ensure their correctness. The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program is supported by the Ohio Department of Natural Resources, the Ohio Water Development Authority, the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency’s Great Lakes Restoration Initiative, and the Ohio Department of Higher Education’s Harmful Algal Bloom Research Initiative Program. The information, findings, and conclusions in this report are those of the authors and do not necessarily represent the views of the funding organizations. Any use of trade, product, or firm names is for descriptive purposes only and does not imply endorsement by the State of Ohio or the U.S. Government. Contact the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program prior to using these data and before citing research and management findings.

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**THE OHIO STATE
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Executive Summary

H2Ohio Wetland Projects Continue to Retain Nutrients

In 2024, the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program (WMP) monitored 45 restoration, enhancement, and construction projects (hereafter Projects), eight of which were intensively monitored Focal Projects. Ten projects had sufficient data to estimate annual net nutrient retention, and all ten projects retained nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P; Table 1). Conversion of agriculture to wetland prevented up to 1.1 lbs. of P loss per acre (average 0.5 lbs./acre). Monitored Projects filtered up to 495 lbs./acre of new incoming P with only one monitored site releasing nutrients (3 lbs. of P; 0.1 lbs./acre). However, the conversion of agriculture to wetland meant that even the Project which released P supported a net reduction in P loading. Monitored Projects filtered up to 5961 lbs. of new incoming N (0–970 lbs./acre). Although most Projects retained nutrients, **nutrient retention within Projects in 2023 and 2024 was lower than expected compared to long-term averages due to dry or drought conditions.** With lower stream flows, less flooding, and less runoff, the nutrient retention potential of wetland Projects was not fully met due to decreased delivery of nutrient-laden water.

Table 1. Estimated retention of phosphorus (P) and nitrogen (N) in H2Ohio wetland Projects with sufficient data. Positive values indicate net retention (including both filtration of incoming nutrients, and P runoff prevention from conversion of agriculture to wetland) of nutrients during the 2024 water year (October 1–September 30). Lbs./acre = pounds per acre of restored wetland.

Project	Description	Total P		Total N	
		lbs.	lbs./ acre	lbs.	lbs./ acre
Oakwoods	Isolated pools, one floodplain pool	117	1.1	0	0
Forder Bridge	Tile-drain catchment-fed treatment train	43	2.2	34	6.8
St. Joe Restoration	Tile-drain catchment-fed treatment train	49	0.5	410	12.4
Redhorse Bend	Floodplain	36	0.7	58	1
Magee Marsh	Reconnected diked coastal marsh	43	0.2	689	4
Springcreek	Side-channel wetland	87	2.5	1052	42
Tipp City	Side-channel wetland	50	4.4	1121	112
Burntwood	Pumped flow-through wetland	297	9.5	5961	221
Brooks Park	Flow-through wetland	57	11	4316	863
Walnut Creek	Side-channel wetland	534	29	4701	270
MEDIAN		54	2	871	27

Balancing Connection and Water Residence Time Maximizes Nutrient Retention

Connecting wetland Projects to water sources with elevated nutrient concentrations maximizes nutrient retention. Projects that receive drainage from large areas that export nutrients (e.g., agricultural land) and hold that water for extended periods (days or more), retain the most nutrients. However, when conditions are dry, as in the drought experienced by most of Ohio in

2024, fewer nutrients are transported in the Lake Erie watershed, including to wetland Projects¹. A successful but resource-intensive strategy to maximize nutrient retention in dry years is to actively move water (e.g., pump water) from high-nutrient rivers, streams, and other water bodies into treatment systems. The Burntwood-Langenkamp Wetland Conservation Area in Mercer County provides an example. Here, an actively managed pump moves water from the high-nutrient Burntwood Creek into the wetland when flow is too low to passively flood.

Wetland designs must account for a range of possible weather conditions and should aim to capture nutrients in runoff and floodwater but also to hold water long enough for biological and chemical processes to retain nutrients. This requires accurate knowledge of drainage and consideration of the shape, size, and landscape position of the as-built wetland. For example, floodplain and side-channel wetlands are designed to fill from adjacent rivers. If pumps are not used, these wetlands passively fill when the water level of the river exceeds the elevation of its connection with the wetland. If the elevation at this connection is too high, the wetland will rarely, if ever, flood and will not be able to process nutrients in the river that bypasses it. If the elevation of the connection is too low, water may flow into the wetland and right back out. Pumps and water level control structures may have costs but can improve connectivity and residence time. Therefore, H2Ohio projects should consider hydrological design choices relative to the location within the watershed that optimize its nutrient reduction potential. **Wetland design reports should provide supporting technical details including (but not limited to):**

- characteristics of the wetland’s source water including, as relevant, the expected drainage area of the Project, its dominant land use(s), and the degree to which engineered drainage systems like agricultural drainage tiles and/or storm drain networks contribute,
- the expected frequency of inundation for specific locations or inlet structure elevations,
- the expected residence times within pools and along flow paths,
- the location and elevation of outlet structure(s), and
- if drainage infrastructure like water level control structures and/or pumps will be installed, information about how these will be used to manage Project hydrology.

Vegetative Communities Feature High Nutrient Storage Capacity

In new wetland projects in which existing vegetation was removed and seeding occurred, wetland vegetation nutrient stocks (measurements of total vegetation nutrient within a Project at a point in time) quickly increased following construction (1–3 years). Nutrients absorbed by plants can be a mix of existing nutrients and “new” nutrient inputs. Nutrient retention by plants increases as vegetation establish and grows. Conversely, in Projects where restoration doesn’t disturb existing vegetation (e.g., coastal diked wetland enhancements), vegetation nutrient stock can start high, exceeding total annual nutrient inputs. These high initial plant nutrient stocks are not equivalent to new nutrient filtration but do reduce nutrient losses from the wetland. Additionally, increases in vegetation nutrient stock over time following restoration likely include

¹ Hounshell, A., L. Johnson, and R. Stumpf. 2024. Nutrient and environmental factors regulating western Lake Erie cyanobacterial blooms. *Aquatic Ecosystem Health & Management* 26:63–75.

some capture of new nutrients. When conditions limit plant growth, such as the drought seasons in 2023 and 2024, new nutrient retention in plants is diminished but not eliminated.

The longevity of plant nutrient storage ranges from less than one year to multiple years. Durations of plant nutrient storage, the rate of plant decay and release of nutrients, and other methods of nutrient capture by plants (e.g., sedimentation) are currently under investigation through supplemental funding (Harmful Algal Bloom Research Initiative). In many Projects, Cattails (*Typha* spp.) contributed the most to nutrients in plant biomass. However, Cattails tend to outcompete other species, lowering biodiversity and habitat value. Using data from H2Ohio Projects with more diverse plant communities, the WMP has identified specific wetland plant species that feature high nutrient storage capacity but also promote biodiversity, including Broadleaf arrowhead (*Sagittaria latifolia*), American water plantain (*Alisma subcordatum*), Soft rush (*Juncus effusus*), Woolgrass (*Scirpus cyperinus*), and Pickerelweed (*Pontederia cordata*).

Soil Conditions Within Wetlands that Promote Nutrient Retention

Most soils monitored in H2Ohio Projects have moderate to high capacity to retain additional phosphate. On average, soil phosphate sorption capacity (SPSC) values have increased, but additional analysis is required to affirm the cause of this increase. In many wetland Projects, soil is disrupted during construction due to earth-moving associated with pool excavation, flow path routing, berm construction, etc. The observed SPSC increases may thus be due to changes in soil chemistry, removal and/or placement of soils with greater sorption capacity, accumulation of new incoming sediment with capacity to sorb phosphorus, or some combination of these. Continued analysis of existing data and monitoring is being supported by a supplemental U.S. Environmental Protection Agency Great Lakes Restoration Initiative grant to evaluate the efficacy of SPSC to predict wetland nutrient removal effectiveness.

2024 Monitoring Program Benefits and Accomplishments

H2Ohio WMP Volunteered in Response to ODNR Request for Proposal Review- The Wetland Monitoring Program (WMP) volunteered to convene a panel of 12 experts to review 13 H2Ohio wetland proposals in response to an Ohio Department of Natural Resources (ODNR) request for assistance. As reviewers, WMP researchers noted which proposed projects would likely retain meaningful nutrient loads. These insights were directly used to improve selection criteria and design of funded Projects. In addition, researchers identified documentation needs to ensure relevant information was obtained for all future proposed Projects.

Leveraged Resources to Better Inform Design and Management Decisions- H2Ohio WMP funding (ODNR, Ohio Water Development Authority) supports data collection to assess the magnitude of nutrient load reduction. In other words, the primary goal is to answer the question: *Do H2Ohio wetland Projects retain nutrients?* However, to inform wetland design and management, understanding what promotes nutrient retention is needed. The WMP sought additional funding to address questions related to *how* wetlands retain nutrients. In 2024, this effort resulted in obtaining a second U.S. EPA GLRI award and two ODHE HABRI awards. Collectively, these efforts also support student training. In 2024 alone, the WMP partnered with

at least five master's or doctoral students and provided monitoring experience to approximately 20 undergraduate students, many of whom have conducted independent research projects and presented their results at scientific and management meetings.

Shaping a Robust Monitoring Program for Science-Based Management- The H2Ohio WMP began as the first H2Ohio Projects were completed in 2020 and 2021. Similar coordinated programs often spend years developing protocols, but the WMP's adaptive approach embraced that early data collection, while not perfectly optimized, would generate valuable information and learning opportunities. Preliminary data in 2021 and 2022 established baseline conditions, informed protocols and data management infrastructure, and directed sampling designs². In 2023, sufficient monitoring had been completed in select Projects to meaningfully estimate annual nutrient retention³. In 2024, the H2Ohio WMP Framework was finalized to establish more comprehensive guidelines regarding how to select Projects for monitoring, parameters measured, and sampling frequency⁴. The updated Framework describes the Program's Guiding Principles: (1) a commitment to responsible, open, sound science, (2) cultivating a community of researchers, professionals, and partners, (3) learning by doing in an adaptive framework, (4) focus on wetland function, and (5) building a foundation for long-term monitoring.

Next Steps

The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program fills a critical knowledge gap for Ohio and the nation by evaluating the nutrient retention function of diverse restored wetlands over time, not just immediately post-construction. Within the first years of a new wetland's construction, plant communities are still establishing, and soil conditions are still equilibrating. Abnormally dry or wet conditions can skew results towards over- or under-estimating longer-term function. Restored and constructed wetlands are rarely adequately monitored⁵. Data from one of the few systems with long-term monitoring (the Old Woman Creek Wetland, Huron, OH) demonstrates that a **minimum of three years of data** is needed to accurately assess trends. **Conclusions drawn from the few years of data collected may underestimate the long-term ability of H2Ohio wetlands to mitigate nutrient loading because of drier-than-average conditions in 2023 and 2024.** In addition, new technologies and approaches are constantly being developed and implemented.

² H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program. 2022. H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program: 2022 Annual Progress Report. Ohio Department of Natural Resources, Office of Coastal Management. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/CVBSX>

³ Lake Erie and Aquatic Research Network, Wetlands and Water Quality Group. 2023. H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program: 2023 Annual Progress Report, Vol. 1. Ohio Department of Natural Resources, Office of Coastal Management. <https://osf.io/gef6d/>

⁴ H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program, 2024. *H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program: Monitoring Framework*. Kinsman-Costello, L.E., K. Fussell, C. Winslow, J. Kerns, O.F. Schloegel, R. Mendonça, R. Becker, T. Bridgeman, K. Doro, S. J. Jacquemin, L. Johnson, G. Liu, K. McCluney, H. Michaels, W.R. Midden, S. Newell, M. Back, L. Brown, I. Rahman, and Z. Swan. Lake Erie and Aquatic Research Network (LEARN) for the Ohio Department of Natural Resources (ODNR). Columbus, OH, USA.

⁵ Anderson, K.J., B. Adhikari, O.F. Schloegel, R. M. Mendonca, M.P. Back*, N. Brocato*, J.A. Cianci-Gaskill, S.E. McMurray, C. Bahlai, D.M. Costello, L.E. Kinsman-Costello. 2024. We know less about phosphorus retention in constructed wetlands than we think we do: A quantitative literature synthesis. *Ecological Indicators*. 169.

Change Log

On February 4, 2026, Version 2 of the present report was created. Version 2 addresses and fixes a mistake in the Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration nutrient filtration and consequent total retention value calculations. An overview of the changes per section is outlined below.

Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration

Note: the updated nutrient filtration and filtration values were calculated after fixing a mistake in the input hydrology data that were used in the original value calculations. Nutrient filtration and retention values were updated throughout the tables and text of Version 2 to match new values (Table 1).

Table 1. Previous and new values for water volume, nutrient filtration, and nutrient retention. Version 2 (V2) addresses and fixes a mistake in the Redhorse Bend Preserve Wetland Restoration nutrient filtration and consequent total retention value calculations.

Parameter	Previous Values (V1)	New Values (V2)
Inflow	54,000 m ³	21,894 m ³
Total P received		10.38 lbs.
Total P filtered	6.6 lbs.	1.19 lbs.
Total P retained	42 lbs.	36 lbs.
Total P retained per acre	0.9 lbs.	0.7 lbs.
Total N received		119.3 lbs.
Total N filtered	98 lbs.	57.8 lbs.
Total N retained	98 lbs.	57.8 lbs.
Total N retained per acre	3.9 lbs.	1 lb.
DRP received		2.7 lbs.
DRP filtered	1.6 lbs.	0.57 lbs.
Nitrate+nitrite received		63.7 lbs.
Nitrate+nitrite filtered	35 lbs.	49.7 lbs.
Ammonium N received		1.46 lbs.
Ammonium N filtered	-1.3 lbs.	0.03 lbs.